
AN ANALYTICAL APPROACH TO THE ELIMINATION OF CORRUPTION

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Abstract.

The purpose of this article is to fight against corruption, and it is to consider the philosophical aspects of the factors that cause it and the mechanisms of its elimination. It is important to strengthen the inevitability of punishment for corrupt behavior, as well as to implement measures against the aspects that cause it.

Key words.

corruption, political institutions, corrupt environment, freedom of social thought.

The fact that today's societies reach their stages of development through their existing regimes and properly functioning political institutions is being proven by further scientific research. So, the reasons why countries face problems and obstacles in terms of development do not depend on external factors, but mainly depend on the country's properly implemented management procedures. While analyzing the countries of the world, noting that there are almost no countries without such shortcomings and problems, attention should be paid to one aspect. In other words, it is necessary to take into account the level of developing ways of solving problems and fulfilling the demands of the people to the state. Based on this, it can be said that some of the shortcomings of the state in its management can be the basis for corrupt situations. If the problem in the system is not solved in time, it can certainly spread widely and rise to the level of the system.

The level of corruption in some countries of the world has reached a surprising level. There may be several main reasons for this. For example, in societies with political instability, economic difficulties, and social problems, corrupt conditions are formed by themselves. It should be understood that the development of punishments for corrupt behavior does not lead to its elimination. Fighting corruption by eliminating the conditions and causes that cause it and philosophically analyzing it will allow positive results. In this place, the ancient philosopher Plato quotes this in his Laws. It should be said that any work does not end with doing something, getting (achieving something), establishing: no, the

work that is done only when the means to preserve what came into the world is found, should be considered as a fully completed work. ; otherwise the whole lacks something[1]. That is, if the adopted law does not produce the desired result, it does not make a change in practical life, determines the importance of the law. Laws are not only a mechanism of punishment, but they should include prevention of crime and elimination of the ways that cause it. When countries face such problems, they often try to change the lens by citing social, economic, political, and natural problems for the purpose of ideological manipulation and concealment of their own problems. Of course, this cannot be a solution. The state, first of all, should want to improve the situation and start positive actions in this way. It is necessary to eliminate the critical obstacles that it has created, to make decisions for the interests of the majority instead of the decisions taken in the interest of the minority, and to apply legal practice that takes into account the future.

Perhaps the state, along with effective enforcement of laws, should implement "freedom of social thought" programs based on providing adequate education and eliminating poverty. This means that the presence of feelings such as literacy, loyalty, patriotism, self-sacrifice in officials and civil servants, which are considered to be the cause of such situations, does not ensure the elimination of the problem. In this place, the elimination of evil from the thinking of the population over time and the formation of a ruling class that really wants to do this can ensure the positive result of the existing reality. Moral values formed in the mind of the society are important in the fight against corruption. That is, principles such as honesty and correctness, justice and equality protect individuals from various injustices in mutual relations. After all, a developed society without corruption can be established only with the help of citizens who are mentally mature and anti-corruption-minded [2].

Various forms of corruption have accompanied mankind since ancient times. At present, corruption is manifested in various forms in proportion to the expansion of the types of social activities of mankind. This can be attributed to the expansion of world trade, the existence of global crime syndicates, the expansion of international aid to underdeveloped countries, the imperfection of the Internet and the system of criminal responsibility.

We can see that today's scientific research proves that the essence of corruption does not originate only from helplessness, as some people think. we observe that there will be officials. This also shows that no amount of propaganda will show any practical results if the education formed in thinking does not change.

As shown in the research, it is necessary to fight against only the black forms of corruption, and the people should begin to accept its lighter forms, gray and white corruption, as wrong, that is, they should make a change in thinking. Considering that the subjects who allow this are recognized on both sides, it shows that the giving party is not always innocent.

To sum up, this is definitely a process formed in connection with the ancient history of mankind. It is not only the ordinary people or the government who understand that it is a vice, but it is not only the formation of a unified mindset, it is not only a fight against the vice, but also a clear assessment of the causes that cause it., starting the elimination mechanisms, laying the foundations for a new thinking society by reforming the education system, and certainly involving the education layer with such a view can give the intended result. Of course, every country forms its own attractiveness with the creation of such conditions, if the country creates an unattractive mood in the country with its environment, it can lose its intelligentsia or potential [3]. This can certainly affect the future plans and potential of each country.

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